

Effects of ICT in Teaching and Learning Mathematics in Senior High Schools: A Case Study of Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region

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DECLARATION

Candidate’s Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis is the result of my own work submitted to the school of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education, C. K. Tadam University of Technology and Applied Sciences, for the award of a degree in Master of Philosophy in Mathematics Education and to the best of my knowledge, no part of it has been published or submitted to any university for the award of any other degree except where reference is made in the text in recognition of the efforts of other scholars.

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Supervisor’s Declaration

I hereby declare that the preparation and presentation of this thesis was duly supervised in accordance with the guideline on supervision of thesis laid down by the C.K. Tadam University of Technology and Applied Sciences.

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ABSTRACT

It is imperative to state that both Mathematics and Information and Communication Technology constitute important disciplines of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education that play an inextricable and profound role in stimulating innovation and creativity in a society riddled with numerous challenges in which the educational environment is not exempted. The overarching tenacity of this exploration was to examine the effects of ICT in coaching and learning Mathematics in Senior High Schools with focus on the Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region. The study engaged both purposive and random sampling techniques and primary data elicited with the aid of structured questionnaire designed based on a five point Likert Scale and semi-structured interview. Data elicited from the field was analyzed with both descriptive and explanatory techniques. Frequencies, means, medians, standard deviations and graphs were employed as tools of analysis with the service of Microsoft Excel and drawing from the standpoint of the outcomes, suffice to conclude that incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instructions has optimistic and noteworthy impact on the outcome of students' academic performance in Mathematics and as well stimulate positive, interactive, collaborative and multidimensional learning environment despite several barriers and challenges including lack of curriculum materials as well as professional skills and knowledge gaps due to lack of professional training programs. This is therefore closely followed with recommendations to help address the challenges.

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my family and the Mathematics Department of Presbyterian Senior High School, Begoro

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

➤ *Background to the Study*

Arguably, the fundamental essence of the Mathematical philosophical constructs, axiom, theorem and proofs is not to only analyze and evaluate complex arithmetic units but also individual relations and social structures and how to resolve non-routine problems in an ever-evolving and increasingly complex and problem riddled society. However, it is common knowledge that both Mathematics and digital technology are twin-disciplines of STEM-education with profound and inextricable significance geared towards stimulating human development and social transformation in the scientific community (Daniel et al., 2015).

From a global point of view, a recent report based on seminal works by the Developments in Intercontinental Mathematics and Science Scholarship (TIMSS) and other global benchmark standards such as the Progress in Intercontinental Reading Literacy Study (PIRL) and Package for Intercontinental Student Assessment (PISA) reported that Finland and Singapore have been best countries with quality education based on their academic excellence and remarkable achievements in Science and Mathematics education which is anchored on the legacy of digital technological affordances (Tan, Low, & Hung, 2017). To emphasize further, the inextricable role of Mathematics and digital technology as twin-subjects of STEM-based education in a highly integrated and interdependent society driven by the wave and proliferation of digital technology can neither be overemphasized nor gainsaid. For instance, fueled by the exponential wave of the digital economy and IT revolution, the global educational landscape has experienced a significant drift from mass education system characterized by conventional pedagogical orientation to a more revolutionized and learner-centered system that stimulates a cooperative and collaborative as well as pragmatic and practical-based learning with immediate feedback, improved academic excellence and achievement of learners in a globalizing environment (Mphale & Mhlauli, 2014).

However, in an ever-evolving and increasingly competitive global environment which is the legacy of globalization and socio-economic integration in the information driven world which elucidates the need for excellent academic performance that ultimately promotes student and graduate advancement and employability in the job market (Mphale & Mhlauli, 2014). Mathematics as a STEM-based discipline is dubbed as the master and gatekeeper of all disciplines relative to its inextricable contribution towards improving learners deductive reasoning, critical thinking and problem solving skills in an ever-evolving and competitive socio-economic and technological environment (Maganga, 2016).

Moreover, there is a growing consensus scholarly view that the “*art of problem-solving is the heart of Mathematics*”. Grounded on this basis suffice to establish that Mathematics constitutes a driver of change in a rapidly changing world riddled with myriad complexities and challenges that permeates every facet of individual social life and the scientific community as a whole. As a global discipline, the drive of Mathematics education is to enhance learners’ Mathematical competence and critical thinking talents in problem solving both in their career and individual social lives (Donaldson, 2011).

Mathematics has occupied an exclusive space as a core discipline in both national and international curricular of the global educational landscape. More importantly, it constitutes one of the compulsory entry requirements into virtually every tertiary institution in the world (Rijal, 2020). In furtherance, research scholars in Mathematics asserts that Mathematics as a STEM based discipline sharpens the mindset of learners and as well enhances their spatial power, logic and critical thinking skills for which reason, it has been considered the heart and integral part of every successful career. Taking into consideration of this critical role, it has been given a special space in both basic and second cycle educational curricular in many countries globally (Rijal, 2020).

However, given the overwhelming benefits and contributions of quality Mathematics education, this result is at odds with the case of many third world countries characterized by infrastructure deficit with increasing attrition rate. This as a consequence seeks to establish that students’ performance and academic achievement in Mathematics in many developing countries is quite dismal and therefore requires concerted efforts of major stakeholders with appropriate policy frameworks and curriculum reforms that best reflects contemporary academic learning activities taking into consideration of the profound role digital technology (Amponsah-Tawiah, 2020).

For instance, (Korbel, 2015) asserts that students’ performance and academic achievement based on national and international benchmark performance and assessment standards in on declining trajectory with increasing cause for concern going forward. This assertion is corroborated by (Adolphus, 2011) that students’ academic performance in Mathematics has been consistently proven dismal and consequently require curricular reforms taking into consideration the significant contributions of digital technology. Grappled with this debilitating performance underscores the need for curriculum reforms that takes into consideration of context related factors such as socio-economic, environmental, innovations and cultural related factors that drive student-centered and benefit-based learning. However, leveraging the wave and proliferation of the ICT revolution constitutes a necessary driver that propels innovation and reformation of the educational landscape with improved collaboration, flexibility and efficiency in lesson planning and delivery accompanied with rapid response and feedback (Daniel et al., 2015).

More importantly, (Keong, Horani, & Daniel, 2015) emphasizes that ICT support contemporary teaching and learning strategies, concepts and theories such as the constructivists' pedagogical approach that promotes cooperative, collaborative, interactive and problem-solving approach of teaching and learning Mathematics. Moreover, driven by globalization and socio-economic integration, ICT is considered the driver of innovation and solutions to all the challenges and inefficiencies derailing the educational environment notably in the context of third world countries with infrastructure and resource constraints. ICT provides practical-based and student centered teaching and learning activities with improved recollection and application of knowledge in the increasing complexity of the society (Das, 2019). In addition, in view of exponential rise of the digital economy, requires a corresponding transformation and pedagogical reorientation and teaching strategies to ensure improvement in conceptual understanding as well as arithmetic and problem-solving skills and general Mathematical literacy of learners (Joshi, 2017). However, in recognition of the overwhelming significance of ICT and expanding attrition rate in Mathematics constituted the crux of this research.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

Considering the enormous and colossal investment made by governments in educational reforms, the quality of performance in Mathematics across the various levels of education has not adequately commensurate with the expenditure made in the sector despite the tremendous educational reforms by policy makers including the Ministry of Education (Poku, 2019).

Student academic performance in Mathematics has been dwindling and deteriorating dramatically and has generally been assessed to be poor which in effect exacerbates the declining trend of conscription in Science and Mathematics programs at the tertiary level accompanied with fragmented knowledge and deficit in Mathematics literacy skills (Korbel, 2015) with the need to incorporate innovative means of learning to improve students literacy and general performance in Mathematics in order to drive educational progress and national socio-economic development by leveraging the exponential advancement and proliferation of modern technology.

The issue of unfortunate learner attainment in Mathematics in secondary schools is not a country specific challenge but a universal problem faced by many countries globally (Rijal, 2020). In a global perspective, the seeming development of declining academic accomplishment of students in Mathematics education as reported by the Trends in Intercontinental Mathematics and Science Education (TIMSS) is a global and universal phenomenon and as a consequence stimulates the need for global reforms (Korbel, 2015).

In the context of Africa however, common causes that further aggravates this abysmal performance have been attributed to the conventional and rote instructional system, infrastructure deficit and resource constraints, poor attitude and deficit mindset as well as poor Mathematical foundation that ultimately precipitate into phobia for Mathematics by learners of the subject (Tachie, 2020). This is empirically corroborated by (Rijal, 2020) in which factors that aggravates the abysmal performance of students are attributed to the conventional rote instructional system, resources constraints and infrastructure deficit, poor Mathematical foundation as well as poor attitude and deficit mindset which precipitates into phobia for Mathematics by learners of the subject.

These reports of abysmal performance of students in Mathematics is reechoed by (Cofie, 2021) where he categorically stated that students performance in Mathematics across all levels of education in Ghana is quite dismal which is attributable to problem-solving deficiencies, stereotyped and negative perceptions about the subject relative to individual past experience. Moreover, (Annie, 2021) alluded to the fact that the low academic attainment of learners in Mathematics in Senior High Schools is occasioned by "variations in pedagogical orientation".

In line with reports from the discoveries of (Evans, 2013), the World Bank Group and the Ministry of Education, Science, Sports & Culture reported that students performance in the educational sector is declining in significance importance which in effect exacerbates the seeming trend of poor performance of students. Moreover, evidence of widespread reports of poor performance of students is deeply entrenched in performance outcomes of national assessments standards and benchmarks in the BECE and WASSCE examinations due to poor comprehension of basic Mathematical concepts and procedures which in effect undermines students Mathematical competence and numeracy skills (Tawiah, 2020).

As a consequence, it is believed by educational researchers and policy makers that modern ICT constitutes a driver for innovation and educational transformation accompanied with faster, efficient, convenient system of facilitating teaching and learning Mathematics accompanied by greater experience of flexibility by both teachers and students inclusive relative to its compatibility with numerous Mathematics software including GeoGebra, Geometry software, algebraic and statistics etc (Chimuka, 2017). For instance, a report by the Ministry of Education revealed that 87% of Senior High Schools in Ghana are adequately equipped with ICT facilities despite a colossal investment to integrate ICT to the country's educational curriculum, most instructors neither integrate nor incorporate ICT to facilitate teaching and learning activities in the classroom relative to low competences as well as resource and time constraints (Ministry of Education, 2009).

This as a consequence aggravates the increasing style of low academic attainment of learners in Mathematics that further exacerbates the declining trend of enrolment in STEM related programs at the tertiary level. In response to this growing concern, it is observed that research with respect to ICT in Mathematics as a sub-discipline of education in the Ghanaian perspective is woefully scanty and this elucidates the need to fill this gap by gauging the significance of incorporating ICT in training and learning Mathematics in Senior High Schools relative to the exponential advancement and proliferation of the IT revolution. A case study of the Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region of Ghana.

➤ *Purpose of the Study*

The central resolution of the study was to assess the effects of ICT in instructing and learning Mathematics as a sub-discipline in STEM education in the Ghanaian perspective. The study focused specifically on the Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region of Ghana where the effects of incorporating ICT in instructing and learning Mathematics in STEM schooling is less-explored. To achieve this, the researcher developed the following specific objectives to help achieve the main purpose of the study.

➤ *The Precise Objectives of the Study are;*

- *To explore the accessibility of ICT infrastructure or otherwise in the Fanteakwa Senior High Schools*
- *To ascertain whether the available ICT infrastructure support effective teaching and learning Mathematics or otherwise.*
- *To examine the knowledge and competence of Mathematics teachers towards incorporating ICT in instructing and learning Mathematics.*
- *To assess the effects of employing ICT in senior high school Mathematics teaching and learning*
- *To determine the variables regulating the usage of ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning.*

➤ *Research Questions*

- *Is there ICT infrastructure or otherwise in the Fanteakwa Senior High Schools?*
- *Which available ICT tools support effective teaching and learning Mathematics in the Fanteakwa North and South Districts Senior High Schools?*
- *How competent and knowledgeable are Mathematics teachers towards utilizing ICT apparatuses in math instruction and learning?*
- *What is the impact of utilizing ICT in Mathematics education and study in Senior High Schools?*
- *What are the factors affecting the utilization ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning?*

➤ *Significance of the Study*

The outcome of the study would have socio-economic and theoretical relevance;

The investigation will add to the wealth of knowledge and using current academic and research publications as a source of information and as well build the framework for future research on the subject. Moreover, the research will enormously be useful to governments, policy makers, educators, researchers and stakeholders in the educational setting by providing insight and roadmap on ad hoc reforms of policy frameworks relative to how to improve teaching and learning activities on practical-based system in STEM related subjects in various Senior High Schools. The study will be of tremendous significance to the Ministry of education and Senior High Schools in the Fanteakwa districts as a precept of policy formulation and decision making tool through identification of the barriers and challenges affecting performance of students in Mathematics with proposed recommendations to redress the challenges. The study will also aid in the exploration of ICT as a tool for development and integration of knowledge, explore more concepts and ideas that will help students craft and integrate ideas towards understanding, development and application of knowledge in real life phenomena.

The study is also a culmination of research focused on Mathematics and STEM education in general and the learning outcome of students in Mathematics. Moreover, this research is motivated by the interest of the researcher in Mathematics and the need to address the concerns and challenges of poor performance in the subject with improved appreciation of Mathematical literacy among Senior High School students and the larger populace.

➤ *Limitations of the Study*

- *The following Represent a Few of the Study's Limitations:*

It is impossible to address all facets and components of a research project of this size since it is so vast. Moreover, literature around the subject matter is woefully scanty within the Ghanaian context and this constituted one of the major constraints affecting the outcome of the research work.

Additionally, due to Covid-19 safety protocols and other measures implemented by the relevant case studies to prevent contracting and spreading the virus, the researcher was limited by time and had limited access to the pertinent data needed to accomplish the study's goal. Finally, some of the views and opinions expressed in this study are those of the researcher and may not produce accurate results if implemented.

➤ *Delimitation of the Study;*

Though the research draw insights from Senior High Schools in the Fantekwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region. However, not all Senior High Schools students in the districts comprised the study's intended audience. The research and its findings were only limited to the consequences of using ICT in senior high school Mathematics instruction and learning and covered only Mathematics and ICT students and teachers of the Fantekwa North and South Senior High Schools.

➤ *Organization of the Study*

The entire research work was organized into five major chapters outlined as follows;

Chapter One: This takes about the topic by providing insight into background, statement of the problem, research objectives and research questions, scope of the study and significance of the study. Chapter two deals with the review of relevant and related literature on the subject matter and focuses mainly on the conceptual review, theoretical and empirical reviews respectively. Chapter three; presents the methodology used in collecting the relevant and necessary data required to achieve the purpose of the study. These include the research design, study population, sampling strategy, sample size, research tools utilized to gather the data, data collection method, and data analysis. The field survey data were analyzed and synthesized in chapter four, along with the main conclusions and an explanation of the findings. A summary of the research's findings, conclusions, and suggestions were offered in Chapter 5.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

➤ *Introduction*

The consequences of integrating ICT in the instruction of mathematics in senior high schools are reviewed in this chapter, which addressed the status of the research in that area. This chapter consist mainly of the conceptual review, theoretical and empirical reviews respectively. The theoretical lens of the study captured the Technological Acceptance Model, the Socio-Cultural theory of learning respectively.

➤ *Conceptual Review*

• *The Concept of ICT*

Arguably, modern Information Communication Technology is deeply entrenched in every socio-economic, political, environmental and cultural facets of life relative to its significant role in storage, management and efficient dissemination of information globally.

However, information technology has been described as a global management approach used in the handling of information and its use in socioeconomic, environmental, and cultural challenges. It is also classified as a scientific, technological, and engineering field (Das, 2019).

ICT has also been defined as an integrated set of technological devices designed to create, store, manage and disseminate information (Bam, 2021). ICT tools on the other hand constitutes a combination of both hardware and software to form a wide range of multimedia systems and digital resources strategically integrated to achieve a particular purpose. Some examples of ICT tools include; Desktop & system units, digital & online libraries, LAN, cloud-computing, digital cameras, internet etc (Das, 2019).

In effect, ICT is dubbed as a set of tools, equipment's and services including telecommunication equipment, information technology equipment, information and communication activities as well as internet and network services which are integrated to serve a particular purpose (Ata-Baah, 2020).

• *Benefits of ICT in Education*

The advent and proliferation of Information Communication Technology has created a more liberalized, dynamic and complex socio-economic environment with rising competition and steady advancement of global economies towards a digitalized world.

For instance, the swifter evolution of information and communication technology has contributed significantly in revolutionizing the entire universal educational system from conventional to modern system giving students easy access to academic resources through internet access, virtual or online education, information access, sharing and storage of academic materials and ease in communication which ultimately enhances academic activities and consequently improved academic performance (Grewal, 2020).

More importantly, integration of ICT tools in education also contributes significantly to transformation of the educational environment from conventional to virtual and mobile systems that allow students to carry their education in their pockets with improved learning efficiency and problem solving skills with improved quality of mathematical understanding (Joshi, 2017).

Ultimately, the contemporary digital and virtual society brought about by technological advancement with competing demands for computers, smart phones, iPad, tablets, laptops and other gadgets such as simple four functional calculators, scientific calculators, and algebra systems all constitute innovations that drive easy teaching and learning activities through internet access, ease in communication, online education, easy access to academic materials for research and development, easy sharing and storage of academic files and virtual or e-learning platforms that enable students carry their education in their pockets and ultimately impact positively on their academic performance (Mukhdoomi, 2020).

Moreover, the integration of ICT in the educational curriculum stimulates positive and interactive as well as collaborative and practical based learning, web-based learning, personal or self-learning accompanied with greater convenience through virtualization of teaching and learning activities (Bam, 2021).

In furtherance, a study conducted by (Chong, Horani, & Daniel, 2005) corroborated that integration of ICT infrastructure in teaching and learning Mathematics contributes towards enhancing students conceptualization of basic Mathematical concepts with improved communication and knowledge sharing, simplification of tedious concepts, promotion of positive learning attitudes with improved numeracy skills. This has been reechoed by (Annie, 2021) that incorporation of ICT into teaching and learning Mathematics fosters a collective, collaborative and interactive learning environment which in effect reciprocates with greater learner sovereignty.

By contrast, a growing interest of researchers and major stakeholders of the scientific community has been rekindled at the turn of the century relative to wide-spread reports of declining performance of students in STEM education coupled with increasing concern of poor performance of students in Mathematics (Korbel, 2015).

This dramatic performance is neither an institution specific nor country specific challenge but rather a global phenomenon. There is a consensus scholarly view that technology is the panacea to the increasing fragmented knowledge and mindset deficit of students accompanied with the increasing phobia for Mathematics by many students globally through its incorporation and providing teaching and learning aid to both learners and instructors alike (Museveni, 2014).

Arguably, technology has become the backbone of every facet of life relative to its significant contribution towards global socio-economic and institutional transformation from conventional to revolutionize and digitalized system accompanied with greater teaching and learning experience. The rise of the virtual economy, which is related to the increasing development and use of computer systems and the widespread use of the internet, has contributed to greater efficiency, safety, and security as well as improved satisfaction and cost minimization. (Mohamed, 2020).

ICT also play an inextricable role in providing materials, tools, and easy access as well as improves the value and quality of education through active and interactive classroom activities. More importantly, incorporating ICT into teaching and learning provide a practical-base experience and hands-on exposure for both instructors and students that ultimately contributes to improving efficiency and time-saving and greater user experience through resource centered approach (Annie, 2021).

In furtherance of this, incorporating ICT also provide an active and interactive teaching and learning process accompanied with digital user experience and simultaneously give both teachers and students the opportunity to control their learning process to be able to absorb reasonable amount of information. This also provide the opportunity to equip students with research & communication skills, effective lesson planning and delivery, hands-on-exposure through demonstrations and project-based learning activities that ultimately conveys a meaningful as well as interdisciplinary system of learning geared towards the ascertainment of curricular objectives (Shiela, 2012).

More so, empirical research has evidenced that integration of ICT tools has been more beneficial in teaching and learning mathematics relative to its crucial role of improving efficiency of lesson planning and delivery, enhanced professional skills of teachers and students' cognitive proficiency and ultimately general performance. Moreover, solicitation of ICT in education aid in improving multi-dimensional learning skills of both students and teachers, enhanced numeracy skills, logical and critical skills, statistics and discrete data analysis (Joshi, 2017).

Ultimately, the inception of modern information and technology as well as its integration to the educational environment has been impactful relative to its compatibility and support of many mathematical concepts and formulae as well as 2D & 3D charts that emphasizes strategic pedagogical shift from the conventional rote learning system to a modernized, efficient, user-friendly and more collaborative approach of teaching and learning which in effect contributes to promoting efficient delivery with enhanced students conceptual understanding (Joshi, 2017).

Deducing from the significant role ICT play from both institutional and personal facets of life globally, suffice to establish that the role and integration of ICT in the educational environment can hardly be over-emphasized nor gainsaid. For instance, incorporation of ICT tools in the educational environment helps to promote both pragmatic and practical-based teaching and learning activities, efficient content delivery, ability to integrate and apply mathematical concepts, its user-friendly and easily adaptable and simultaneously promotes interactive, co-operative and collaborative system of learning in the class-room.

More importantly, it can also be said that ICT supports diversity and support multi-dimensional learning, active participation with improved creation of new ideas and new solutions for real-life problems. It can further be adduced that ICT enhances mobility and accessibility of education as well as teaching and learning materials every time and everywhere through electronic and virtual learning systems (Das, 2019).

Ultimately, application of ICT tools in the educational facet helps students to apply theoretical knowledge into practical learning skills. For instance, empirical research evidenced that ICT is more compatible and supportive to many systems that enable visualization of problems with the application of mathematical tools such as Geogebra, Geometer's Sketchpad, Mathematica, Maple and Drive that support efficient and interactive teaching and learning mathematics in the class-room (Bam, 2021).

Ultimately, successful incorporation of ICT into the Mathematics curriculum sets the trajectory to leapfrogging the educational system taking into consideration of the wave and proliferation of the digital economy that offer several benefits including introduction of new reforms, specialized software, floor robots, data base that promote dynamic learning experience with improved arithmetic learning and problem solving skills of students (Shiela, 2012).

(Ata-Baah, 2020) establish that incorporation of ICT into the Mathematical curriculum enhances the pace of teaching and learning, gives students excitement and improve their confidence, introduces new strategies and as well as style of instruction and learning and improves learners curiosity. Moreover, successful amalgamation of ICT in Mathematics education and learning also enhances efficiency of lesson planning with wider range of resources and accelerates lesson delivery in the classroom.

In addition, (Ata-Baah, 2020) asserted further that incorporation of ICT into the Mathematical curricular in teaching and learning Mathematics provide a great deal of benefits including enhancement of students interactivity and further exploration of new set of ideas and learning skills that ultimately broadens their learning opportunities with improved ability to conjure and make deductive reasoning.

- *Knowledge and Competence of Mathematics Teachers in using ICT Instruments for Mathematics Instruction and Learning.*

Arguably in the educational setting, teacher's professional competence constitutes a fundamental determiner of the quality of students' knowledge while ICT constitutes the key to new solutions driven by the wave and proliferation of the digital economy.

However, there is a growing consensus scholarly view by researchers, managers of corporate institutions and educational psychologists that, the performance and productivity of any Organizations rely extensively on the caliber, competency, and talents of its employees, who are regarded as their most significant assets and trademarks (Oaya et al., 2017).

Deducing from this assertion, suffice to establish that teachers' professional competence, confidence and beliefs as well as professional training constitutes a very crucial factors that determines their ability to incorporate innovative strategies including modern IT infrastructure to boost the overall standard of classroom instruction and learning (Ata-Baah, 2020).

Moreover, it is empirically evidenced that successful ICT integration in Mathematics instruction and learning is determined by variables such as knowledge, skills and professional competence of teachers are supporting that determines students' life-long learning experience as well as further advancement and progression. Moreover, instructor's competence and skills as well as their ability to adjust to new technological innovations determines the worth of instruction and learning in the class-room. For instance, according to (Rangel, 2019), even in the wake of the 21st century, most teachers still have difficulties in adjusting, adopting and integrating new technologies to facilitate effective and efficient teaching and learning in the classroom.

Also, teachers' expertise, skills and competencies constitute the drivers of transformation and performance both within and outside the tutorial room. Moreover, it is believed that individual skills and competences enhances consistency in performance and service delivery, improved service excellence, decline of charge and management and eventually aids in the attainment of better performance. For instance, the new mathematics curriculum post the recent educational reforms lay much emphasis on the integration of ICT in the secondary to improve skill acquisition, creativity and problem-solving skills (Agyei & Voogt, 2010).

More importantly, the capabilities, knowledge, skills and competence of teachers in integrating ICT helps to improve teachers lesson planning and also provide real-life learning experience through pragmatic examples. It is also believed that the knowledge, competence and skills of teachers helps in clear understanding and effective content delivery in the classroom that ultimately enhances the pace improves students' attitude and learning experience (Larkin & Jorgensen, 2016).

As a consequence, it can therefore be deduced that the knowledge and skills as well as competence of teachers clearly define their quality that constitutes a determiner of their ability and flexibility to effectively adjust to new innovations, integrate ideas, efficient planning, effective engagement and quality delivery that in effect stimulate positive attitude of students and better understanding of arithmetic lessons and good performance as the ultimate goal.

Suffice to also establish that teachers' competence determines their ability to adjust to new trends and the ability to incorporate innovative strategies to promote collaborative learning, counter productivity and creativity with improved development of content knowledge and critical thinking skills.

- *Barriers/Challenges of Integrating ICT into Mathematics Curriculum*

The wave and proliferation of modern ICT infrastructure dramatically necessitated a reformation of various business models, processes and procedures with which certain activities and businesses should be executed. For instance, the application of the IT infrastructure has transformed various teaching models and strategies with improved efficiency, service quality and maximization of flexibility. This has also helped to effectively integrate and coordinate as well as harmonize the entire process of process of lesson planning, efficient content delivery as well as promote an active, interactive, collaborative learning process that ultimately contributes to enhancing students' passion, attitude and conceptual understanding of mathematical concepts (Acheampong, 2018).

Conversely, there are other associated factors that impede effective integration and incorporation of ICT tools to effectively achieve curricular activities. Some of these factors have been identified to include changes in educational policy frameworks by successive governments, infrastructure deficits, challenges in both human and materials related constraints, financial constraints relative to high costs associated with the adoption of the appropriate and quality ICT tools (Arthur, 2020).

In furtherance, other considerable impediments that hamper efforts towards integrating ICT into the Mathematics curriculum have been identified to include technical related challenges, knowledge and skills gaps associated with the use of technology, fragmented knowledge and skills due to inadequate professional ICT education and training, culture, attitude and perceptions of both students and teachers, perceived usefulness, perceived risks and ease of use all constitute some of the forces and constraints that affect the integration as well as the incorporation and usage of technological resources in Mathematics education and learning (Arthur, 2020).

In addition, this findings is corroborated by reports from the findings of (Chong, Horani, & Daniel, 2005) relative to the obstacles impeding the amalgamation of ICT in coaching and learning Mathematics and the results from the findings reported barriers including; inadequate time, lack professional training teacher training, lack of professional skills and knowledge relative to how to integrate ICT with the Mathematics curricular as well as infrastructure deficit.

For instance, (Ata-Baah, 2020) opined that a study conducted by the TIMSS reported that there is lack of incorporation and application of computers in Mathematics lesson in many countries with availability of computers. Some of the causes have been attributed to lack of curriculum resources in many schools, hardware and software challenges including technical support services, lack of professional expertise and experience, negative attitude and beliefs of teachers which contributes higher resistance of using ICT tools, lack of professional education and training all constitute some of the barriers and challenges that hamper efforts towards successful incorporation and usage of ICT in coaching and learning Mathematics in many jurisdictions.

Moreover, as reechoed by reports from the findings of (Annie, 2021), few of the obstacles straining successful amalgamation of ICT into the Mathematics curriculum include time constraints, teachers confidence, competence and beliefs. As a consequence, it is imperative to establish that central to the success of incorporating ICT into coaching and learning Mathematics is fundamentally embedded in teacher’s knowledge, attitude, perception, professional competence and passion, perceived benefits involved and availability of infrastructure all constitute some of the necessary determinants or factors affecting the assimilation of ICT tools in coaching and learning Mathematics in various Senior High Schools notably in developing economies with fragmented knowledge and low technological development and infrastructure deficits.

➤ *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

The conceptual structure of a study helps to energize the researcher and ensures advancement of knowledge by igniting and guiding the research enquiry. Moreover, the conceptual framework constitutes a researcher’s peculiar erected model which expounds the affiliation amongst the central variables in the research work and primarily consists of a series of interconnected concepts and overlaps that serve as a guide and iteration of the research questions and how the researcher intends to address the research problem (Mensah, Frimpong, Acquah, Babah, & Dontoh, 2020).

In the context of this research, the conceptual framework intends to provide an overview and explanation of the relationship among the main variables including; the research objectives and questions, the rationale for the theoretical framework as well as the methodological approach and research methods employed to address the research problem.

Fig 1 Suggested I.C.T Tools
Source: Author’s Construction August, 2023.

➤ *Theoretical Literature*

Arguably, theories play a pivotal role in shaping how ideas, concepts and propositions are articulated to convey an overarching purpose of a study and simultaneously serve as an anchor upon which an established body of knowledge is grounded (Awa et al, 2015).

The theoretical lens of this study captured the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Constructivists theory of learning respectively.

- *The Unified Theory of Acceptance and use of Technology (UTAUT)*

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UATUT) constitutes one of the theoretical models of modern innovation and technology embedded on the factors that influences individual recognition and usage of technology in the organizational work environment. The theory constitutes an amalgamation of different technological constructs and models developed to explain individual acceptance and incorporation of modern ICT to achieve both individual and corporate goals including; the technology acceptance theoretical constructs, theory of strategic behavior and dissemination of invention theories respectively. The UTAUT is therefore a synthetization of other theoretical constructs of ICT that gives an extensive intuition into the dynamics influencing behavior of recognition and usage of modern ICT to achieve both individual and work related goals in the organizational setting (Arthur, 2020).

- *Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)*

According a study by (Misango, Njeru & Kithae, 2016), There are some psychological and societal dynamics that influences entities pronouncement to adopt and usage of a new technological invention. These factors have been identified to include; apparent menaces, affluence of use, apparent usefulness, subjective and facilitation conditions respectively. The theory proposes further that both perceived ease of use and apparent convenience institute the two main factors that impacts individual's discernment and attitude towards adopting and usage of technology (Arthur, 2020).

Nonetheless, based on a few arsenal of empirical studies conducted incorporating the Technology Acceptance Model to test individuals adoption and use of different technological innovations including online shopping intentions, electronic collaboration and website use technological innovations are largely based on the apparent risks, ease of use and perceived benefits of any ICT tool all constitute the attitudinal factors that influence individuals towards incorporation and use of technology (Arthur, 2020).

- *Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)*

The Theory of Planned Behavior as a model of technological innovation is based on the assumption that for individuals to adjust and adopt to a new behavior relative to the incorporation and use of technology, they must first create the intension of engaging in that new behavior. The theory proposes further that the intension to incorporate and use a new technology in itself is motivated by some *psychological factors and social norms* respectively (Awuku, 2019).

Perceived behavioral control constitutes the extent to which individuals trust that they can apply control over the new behavior accompanied with incorporating and using such technology. Social norms on the other hand are the pressure that individuals feel within their social environment to engage in the usage of such technology. Most individuals are influenced by their attitudes and perceived social pressure to make evaluations to adopt and use technology (Awuku, 2019).

The rationale and justification for the choice of these theoretical constructs is to enable the researcher to identify and predict individuals' perceptions relative to incorporation and use of ICT for Mathematics instruction and learning in senior high schools. Moreover, this will simultaneously enable the researcher to unearth the underlying factors influencing the adoption or resistance in incorporation and use of technology including perceived risks and perceived benefits respectively. More importantly, this is to further enable the researcher identify the risks perceptions of teachers in adopting and using ICT while proposing certain recommendations to build trust and encourage the incorporation of ICT to advance experience in teaching and learning Mathematics in second cycle institutions.

- *The Constructivists Theory*

Myriad teaching and learning philosophical traditions and strategies have been developed over the past few decades aimed at facilitating effective pedagogical and educational activities in the class-room. Some of these theories have evolved over the period with a conceptual and paradigm shift from teacher-centered approach to student-centered approaches respectively. Relevant to this research is the constructivists' theory which is considered the most contemporary learning theories developed and widely employed to stimulate effective and positive learning among students (Berhane et al., 2020).

The constructivists' theory constitutes one of the contemporary learning paradigms based on a transition from a behaviorists and teacher centered to recognized the role of the teacher as a trainer and important instrument for creating a convenient and interactive educational environment. The constructivists' theory further argue that people actively develop ideas and knowledge through the process of testing and application of learning concepts in different situations in real life phenomena. In effect, this learning theory proposed that new knowledge and ideas previously must be appropriately integrated and applied into existing structures to ensure that it is adequately remembered and received meaning (Woldeamanuel, Abate, & Berhane, 2020).

The rationale for this theoretical underpinning in the context of this research was reinforced by the fact that incorporation of ICT tools for effective pedagogical and educational activities is one of the conceptual underpinning of the constructivist theoretical approach designed to address practical based challenges and students difficulties towards integration and application of knowledge in real life phenomenon.

➤ *Empirical Literature*

According to a study by (Das, 2019) in discovering the role and application of ICT apparatuses in teaching Mathematics using conversational, observational and interpretive methods of approach with secondary literature from journals and monographs. Data obtained was analyzed using document-based analytical approach. Results from the findings revealed that inadequate ICT training, time constraints and lack of teacher confidence and technical support constituted some of the challenges affecting incorporating of ICT implements in teaching and Mathematics.

Moreover, based on a study conducted by (Joshi, 2017) on the influence of ICT in Mathematics teaching revealed that the application of ICT tools in Mathematics provide support to teachers in lesson planning process, improved pedagogical knowledge, enhancing effective teaching strategies and tactics, improved teacher confidence and further development of more subjective ideas in Mathematics education and learning. Relative to these significant contribution of ICT in Mathematics, the study therefore concludes that stakeholders should leverage the advancement and proliferation of modern technology to integrate and utilize ICT tools help improve in-class instruction and learning

In furtherance of this, a research conducted by (Agyei & Voogt, 2010) relative to the usage of ICT in teaching Mathematics in Ghana using interview and survey data survey from Senior High Schools in Ghana. Results from the findings revealed that Mathematics instructors do not sufficiently assimilate ICT in their teaching of Mathematics due to lack of the requisite professional knowledge and ICT training.

Moreover, a study by (Bam, 2021) relative to the amalgamation of ICT in teaching Mathematics based on the perspective of students using a five Likert's scale questionnaire and interview as data collection instruments with 100 students sampled randomly. Data collected was analyzed with the application of SPSS software using means, percentages, standard deviation, and t-test. Results obtained from the discoveries revealed that incorporation of ICT has a positive impact student's attitude, perception and conceptual underrating of mathematics.

In addition to the above, a study by (Annie, 2021) on participants' positive attitude, ICT competence, access to ICT apparatuses, training style and confidence level as key predictors of ICT integration using a sample size of 92 participants constituting mathematics from senior high school. Data obtained and analyzed revealed a positive correlation between positive attitude, ICT competence and access to ICT and instruction variables relative to the stages of incorporation and use of ICT tools in how Mathematics is taught and learned in senior high schools.

More so, a research study by (Acheampong, 2018) on basic school teachers' integration of ICT in coaching and learning Mathematics in the classroom using survey method of research and cluster sampling technique with a sample size of 148 mathematics teachers from the Western Region. Data obtained and analyzed reported that basic school teachers had the requisite ICT knowledge and skills required in integrating ICT for effective teaching and learning Mathematics.

In furtherance of this, (Sheila, 2016) explored the chances and encounters affecting the assimilation and use of ICT in coaching and learning Mathematics at the secondary level in Kenya using a descriptive method of research design and questionnaire and interviews to collect data through purposive sampling technique with sample size of 299 comprising secondary school students and teachers respectively. Statistics acquired from the survey was explored with the application of SPSS using percentages and frequencies. Results from the findings revealed inadequate ICT assimilation in Mathematics education and learning due to lack of requisite professional skills.

More importantly, (Nihuka & Busu, 2015) in their investigation about teachers' experience about specialized improvement programme relative to ICT amalgamation in teaching and learning science and Mathematics in secondary schools using survey method of research design and questionnaire with purposive sampling technique and sample size of 63 to collect data primary data from secondary school teachers. Data obtained was analyzed using data reduction method technique and results from the findings revealed that a significant proportion of teachers had the requisite professional competence in ICT specialized improvement programme and ability to integrate ICT in coaching and learning science Mathematics.

Moreover, according to (Gomez-Garcia, Hossein-Mohand, Trujillo-Torres, & Hossein-Mohand, 2020) in their examination of the relative indicators such as teachers' knowledge, relationship between teachers as well as age and gender to determine teachers' use of ICT in Mathematics education and learning in secondary schools. The study engaged a sample size of 73 and questionnaire to collect data from relevant sources and analyzed with the application of principle component analysis (PCA) and the results showed that teachers' assimilation of ICT in Mathematics education and learning was depended on the accessibility of

ICT resources while gender did not have any influence. Generally, the results revealed that teachers perception and professional competence did not match the require models to assimilate ICT in Mathematics education and learning.

However, deducing from the empirical findings, it is observed that an arsenal of research is conducted relative to the incorporation and use of ICT teaching and learning Mathematics with mixed results from the outcome of their respective findings demonstrating a varied degree of inconsistencies. While some of the results proved positive, others were negative. It is therefore the reason coupled with the increasing concern of stakeholders in the academic attainment of learners in Mathematics in Senior High Schools elucidates the need to assess the upshots of incorporating ICT in coaching and learning Mathematics in Senior High Schools in the Fantekwa North in the Eastern Region of Ghana.

CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ *Introduction*

This chapter outlined the methodology that was used, which mostly included the research design and approach, study population, sampling strategy, and sample size, data collection instrumentation as well as techniques of data collection and analysis, concerns regarding ethics, as well as validity and reliability.

➤ *Research Design*

The design of an exploration constitutes a masterplan that details out the strategic processes and procedures relative to how, where and when statistics is stimulated and scrutinized to achieve the overarching drive of the research work (Creswell, 2018). Generally, there are three widely employed designs in social science research including; exploratory, explanatory and descriptive research strategies correspondingly. The study engaged a convergent technique of research approach with a case study method of orientation. The rationale and justification for the choice of this design is based on the fact that it allows the researcher to collect both quantitative and qualitative types of data from participants of a survey, merge both types of data in order to reduce any form of bias and simultaneously allow the researcher to provide comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the overall results obtained from the research findings where incongruent findings are further given detailed explanations.

➤ *Research Approach*

The approach to a research work constitutes the plan and set of procedures that spells-out the specific steps taken to accumulate, examine and infer data to achieve the purpose of a research work. In the field of social sciences research, there are three main ways of techniques that are frequently used: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed (Gummesson, 2004).

This study engaged a mixed or abduction approach of orientation encompassing both quantitative and qualitative methods of orientation. The qualitative method of approach deals with an inductive approach of collecting text-based data from the participants setting without the use of numerical values in order to explore the understanding and meaning persons or cluster ascribe to a human or social phenomenon. The quantitative method of approach on the other hand deals with the process of testing objective theories in order to ascertain the relationship between variables where numerical numbers are used in data collection, which is then transformed into useful statistics. (Creswell, 2018).

The method in question uses inference to evaluate a predetermined hypothesis in order to determine potential effects resulting from the research problem. It involves inquiries, statistical analysis, and trials that use inferential argumentation to evaluate a current phenomenon in a more accurate and representative real-world setting. (Munot, 2019).

This study employed the abduction or mixed method of orientation consisting of an integration of both quantitative and qualitative techniques respectively. The rationale and justification for the choice of this approach was reinforced by the fact that it allows the investigator to assemble both quantitative and qualitative data from multiple sources in order to gain more insight to understand details of the research problem and in effect contributes to minimizing any form of weaknesses and biases associated with each method of data collection and as well ensure triangulation of results for purpose of reliability and trustworthiness.

➤ *Research Philosophy*

There are four fundamental philosophical viewpoints under which every research work is grounded inclusively; the positivists; constructivists; transformative and pragmatists. This study was reinforced by the pragmatic point of view. The rationale and justification for the choice of this research philosophy is grounded on the circumstance that it is considered more suitable for a mixed method of orientation and simultaneously enables the researcher to focus specifically on the research problem and not the method employed instead and as well mandate the researcher to employ pluralistic or convergent methods of orientation to collect data from multiple sources to explore deeper understanding of the research problem (Creswell, 2018).

➤ *Population of the Study*

Table 1 Population characteristics: Presbyterian Senior High School & New Nsutam Senior High Technical School, Begoro

Parameter	Population
SHS 1	1,322
SHS 2	1, 033
Mathematics Teachers	27
ICT Teachers	9
Total Population	2, 391

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The Population of the study constituted Senior High School students and teachers of the Presbyterian SHS, Begoro and New Nsutem Senior Technical High, Nsutem in the Fantekwa North and South Districts respectively in the Eastern Region while the target population for the study include all core Mathematics students and teachers and ICT students and teachers. The inclusion criteria constitutes all Core Mathematics and ICT students and teachers of the Presbyterian Senior High School, Begoro and the New Nsutem Senior High Technical School, Nsutem in the Fantekwa Districts. The justification for the selection of these cluster of people was reinforced by the general experience of challenges grappled with Senior High School students in conventional teaching and learning Mathematics and its effects on their academic performance. More specifically, the rationale for the choice of the Senior High Schools in the Fantekwa Districts was reinforced by the fact that it has a well-established ICT center but as to whether it is well equipped or integrated into teaching and learning Mathematics is a question that begs for answers which in effect informed the researcher's decision to probe the effects of ICT in teaching and learning Mathematics hence the choice of the Presbyterian Senior High, Begoro and the New Nsutem Senior High Technical School Nsutem, in the Fantekwa North and South Districts of the Eastern Region of Ghana.

➤ *Sampling Technique*

A sampling technique constitutes a method or strategy employed to select participants with common characteristics grounded on the interest of the researcher in order to accomplish the purpose of a study (Bhardwaj, 2019). In the perspective of this exploration, the study engaged a random sampling method to select Core Mathematics and ICT students for the study while purposive sampling procedure was used in choosing the respective teachers for the interviews. The rationale and rationalization for the choice of the random sampling procedure was reinforced by the fact that it is considered unbiased probability sampling method that gave each respondent equal opportunity and chance of being selected to be part of the survey (Ramachandran & Tsokos, 2009).

The purposive sampling technique on the other hand constitutes a feature of qualitative research and a method of non-probability sampling which allows the investigator to identify and select the primary respondents with the necessary characteristics, knowledge, and experience based on the researcher's own judgment and the information necessary on the case under investigation. The simplicity and low cost of this technique were factors that furthered its justification.

➤ *Sample Size*

A sample size of (210) was employed for the study and comprised mainly of Core Mathematics and ICT students and teachers respectively. (36) teachers were purposively selected comprising of (27) Core Mathematics teachers and (9) ICT teachers respectively while (174) students were randomly selected comprising of both Senior High School 1&2 Core Mathematics and ICT students respectively.

It was impracticable to explore the entirety of the population of the study, thus the sample was instead examined, generalized, and inferred to the full population of the study. This fact served as further support for the logic and justification for the sample size of 210. The cost of data collection in relation to financial and time restrictions was one of the major reasons that the sample size of 210 was chosen.

➤ *Sources of Data for the Study*

Every study project uses data from a couple of primary sources. These include the study's substantial data sources, which include first-person accounts gleaned via field surveys via interviews, focus groups, structured questionnaires, and the researcher's own observations that are only used for the study. (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

The global web, which is widely readily available and has already been used for purposes other than the purpose of this study, as well as books, journal articles, reports, and conferences, are among the secondary sources of data. These sources include scholarly literature that has been published and unpublished. (Nguyen, 2017).

This research employed only principal sources of statistics stimulated from field survey with the aid of structured questionnaire with close-ended type questions using the five point Likert's scale and interview guide. The rationale and justification for the choice of the close-ended type questionnaire was influenced by the fact that the questionnaire provided adequate room for participants to respond to questions and as well provided confidentiality, anonymity and convenience to participants. The structured interview guide on other hand contained open-ended type questions offered the interviewer the chance to probe follow-up questions for further clarification in order to delve deeply and explore detailed information about the study problem by allowing interviewees to openly voice their ideas.

➤ *Instrumentation*

Structured questionnaires were one of the various information acquisition devices used in the investigation and semi-structured dialogue guide. The structured questionnaire was designed with a five point Likert Scale while the interview guide consisted a lists of open-ended type of interview questions. Both the questionnaire and semi-structured interview constituted the foundation of the research objectives and questions designed to solicit data to achieve the overarching purpose of the study. In all, (210) sample of inquiry form and interview guide were premeditated and administered to the Schools to solicit the needed primary

data required to achieve the overarching drive of the study. The questionnaire has the advantage of giving anonymity and as well as protects the confidentiality and integrity of participants. The semi-structured interview guide on the other hand provides flexibility to the inquirer for further modification of data collections instruments for further probing to explore detailed and accurate information relative to the research problem.

➤ *Administration Procedure*

An official letter of consent was issued to the schools for executing the research after the investigator had requested the support and authorization of the management of the institutions prior to the data gathering process. The participant consent form contained details including the main purpose of the research work, benefits and risks involved and simultaneously acknowledged the right of the participants to partake, decline or withdraw at stage in the process. The researcher conducted in-person questionnaire administration and interviewing. The schools were issued (174) questionnaire sample packets. Data collection was done in person and it took precisely ten working days to complete the process.

➤ *Method of Data Analysis*

Procedures that include both quantitative and qualitative methods were used. Using Microsoft Excel as a whole, the data gathered from the field survey were evaluated and examined. Relevant tables, charts, frequencies, means, mode and standard deviations were employed as tools of analysis to present comprehensive analysis of data as well as results from the findings in order to achieve the purpose of the study.

The quantitative exploration was essentially statistically imaginative in nature where appropriate tables, graphic representation, frequencies, means, mode and standard deviations were incorporated to organized summaries of what was discovered to provide instances that demonstrate the findings in line with the goals of the study to address the research problem. The rationale for the choice of the descriptive statistics was necessitated by the need to describe the pattern emerged from the data and the interest of the researcher in relating that to the performance of students in Mathematics.

The qualitative method of analysis mainly thematic content analysis. The content analysis use adopt interpretive techniques which is conceived as objective that makes use of coding following identification and categorization of information into themes and subthemes as well as the relationship between the themes materialized from the survey. Qualitative statistics was elicited from the field was given preliminary reading and closely followed by categorization of information into themes and subthemes. Descriptive codes were created post categorization of information that enabled the researcher to avoid potential drifts and to also produce a flexible report based on information elicited from the findings.

➤ *Ethical Consideration*

Before administering the survey and addressing pertinent issues with important employees and fascination groups, the respondents' comprehension and consent were requested in order to elicit the data needed to fulfill the study's objectives. The privacy and confidentiality of responses are also assured because the information requested is for scholarly purposes.

Additionally, the Rules of Conduct and Protocol Review Committee of the C. K. Tadam University of Technology and Applied Sciences will grant its ethical approval. In addition, the purpose of the study as well as the risks and benefits involved were disclosed and all concerns addressed prior to enrolling participants into the study. Consequently, the nature and purpose of the study is to fulfil academic requirement and for that matter, information obtained is used only for the intended purpose without been disclosed to third parties except where permission was granted by participants.

➤ *Validity and Reliability*

Validity and reliability constitute important components in every research inquiry. The validity and reliability of a research work constitute the accuracy and precision of the results obtained from a research study (Nguyen, 2017).

To ensure validity of this study, the statistics collection instruments including inquiry form and dialogue guide were designed and first submitted to my supervisor and some of my colleagues in the teaching field for possible comments, suggestions and corrections respectively. Inputs were made by my supervisor and colleagues in the educational field that helped the researcher to enhance the designed questionnaire to solicit the data required to address the research problem.

CHAPTER FOUR PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Introduction*

This chapter presents the exploration of survey data as well as argument and clarification of key discoveries. Data analysis is both quantitative and qualitative respectively. The quantitative analysis is mainly statistically descriptive using tables, charts, graphs, percentages, frequencies, means, median, mode and standard deviations as tools of analysis with the service of Microsoft Excel to present outcomes from the findings in a comprehensive format. The qualitative data elicited from the field was first sorted and given preliminary reading and closely followed by categorization of information into themes and subthemes. Descriptive codes were created post categorization of information that enabled the researcher to avoid potential drifts and to as well produce a flexible report based on information elicited from the findings.

Table 2 Sample Distribution

Parameter	Frequency	Percent (%)
Students	174	83%
Core Mathematics Teachers	27	13%
ICT Teachers	9	4%
Total	210	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

➤ *Analyzing Statistics on Demographics*

Participants' age as well as gender are two characteristics of the information on demographics gathered for the analysis. Participant gender and age play a significant and profound role in shaping individual's perception, understanding and interpretations ascribed to Mathematics as to whether difficult or otherwise.

Fig 2 Participants Gender Distribution

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

As depicted in figure1, the investigator required to distinguish the set of disparity between sexes of participants of the survey. Grounded on data elicited from the survey, outcomes from the findings emerged that out of the 210 sample of students, (79) representing 38% constituted male students while (95) representing 45% constituted female students respectively. Moreover, results from the findings revealed further that (29) representing 14% constituted male teachers while (7) representing 3% constituted female teachers who participated in the survey. In general, results from the findings seeks to suggest that both set of

gender constituted students and teachers of the various schools and participants of the study which in effect seeks to demonstrate that neither data collection nor results from the findings suffered any form of bias.

Fig 3 Age Distribution
Source: Field Survey, 2023.

As depicted in figure 2, the inquirer pursued to discover the comparative age categories of participants of the survey. Data solicited from the survey revealed that (112) representing 53% were between 15-20 years, (62) representing 30% were 21-25 years, (21) representing 10% were between 26-30 years, (9) representing 4% were between 31-35 years while (6) representing 3% were between 36-40 years respectively.

➤ *Qualitative Statistics Analysis*

Qualitative statistics inquiry was mainly thematic content examination making use of descriptive codes. The descriptive codes were created after sorting, preliminary reading and categorization of information. This was followed by further checking in order to identify major themes and subthemes as well as the frequency and relationship between the themes and subthemes. The rationale and justification for the few sample size for the interview was due to data saturation. Descriptive codes were created including FP1, FP2, FP3, FP4, FP5 & FP6 to represent the identity of six Core Mathematics and ICT teachers selected for the interview. The descriptive codes constituted the means of presentation of qualitative data which enabled the researcher to avoid possible drifts and as well protect the confidentiality and anonymity of participants.

Table 3 Themes & Subthemes Identified from the Survey

Main Themes	Subthemes
Availability of ICT infrastructure in Mathematics Education and Instruction	ICT Tools & Resources
Teachers Assimilation of ICT Tools in Mathematics tuition	Determinants of ICT amalgamation in Mathematics Education and Instruction
Influence of ICT in Mathematics Instruction	Students' perception & Attitude about Mathematics.
Benefits of ICT in Mathematics Instruction	Students' conceptual understanding & performance in Mathematics.

- *Availability of ICT Infrastructure in Teaching and Learning Mathematics*

Under this objective, the investigator pursued to sightsee the accessibility of ICT infrastructure, tools and resources to support Mathematics instruction in the Fanteakwa North and South Districts Senior High Schools in the Eastern Region based on teachers experience. To achieve this aim, the inquirer posed the following question during the interview. *Are there ICT infrastructure and resources available in the school? If yes, then kindly state some ICT the apparatuses and resources available to upkeep coaching and learning Mathematics.*

However, data solicited from the survey turnout that all the six participants *FP1.....FP6* who met the eligibility and inclusion criteria were both ICT and Mathematics. All the six participants selected out of the thirty sample of teachers responded in a yes affirmative in confirmation of the availability of ICT infrastructure and resources that complement teaching and learning activities. Relative to some of the available ICT tools, it also emerged from the findings that some of the available ICT tools and resources that complement teaching and learning activities were identified to include; ICT lab, *desk/table top monitors, system units, mouse, keyboard, connection cables and projectors.* Participants *FP1, FP2, FP3, FP4, FP5 & FP6.* Based on teachers observation and experience, there is the availability of ICT infrastructure and resources as well as tools that support teaching and learning activities in the various senior high schools.

- *Determinants of ICT Incorporation in Teaching and Learning Mathematics*

In this section, the inquirer sought to discover the determinants of incorporating ICT in teaching and learning Mathematics in Senior High Schools. However, data elicited from the findings emerged as follows:

...Based on my experience as a Mathematics teacher, some of the factors that determine teachers amalgamation of ICT tools in Mathematics education are; availability of teaching and learning resources, teacher's professional competence and knowledge in ICT, teacher's motivation, passion, attitude, commitment and willingness to assimilate ICT tools in teaching and learning activities" ... FP1, FP3, FP5 & FP6: Core Mathematics & ICT teachers.

In furtherance, participant *FP2 & FP4* recounted as follows:

..."Based on my observation and experience as a teacher, I know some of the factors or determinants to include both students and teachers attitude and perception about its usefulness, perceived risks and benefits associated with integrating ICT in teaching and learning Mathematics" ...participants FP2&FP4: ICT & Core Mathematics teachers'.

From the findings based on teachers knowledge and experience, various factors were identified as determinants or dynamics that impact teachers assimilation of ICT tools or otherwise in teaching and learning Mathematics some of which included teachers professional knowledge & competence, availability of teaching and learning materials and resources as well as both learners and teachers passion, attitude, commitment and willingness to incorporate ICT tools to or otherwise.

- *Incorporation of ICT in Mathematics Instruction & its Influence on Students Attitude & Perception about Mathematics.*

The overarching drive of this objective was to discover students' attitudes and perceptions relative to the application of ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning based on teachers' classroom experience. The findings based on data solicited from the interviews emerged as follows:

..."Based on my experience in the classroom, I have observed that students are often happy and do enjoy using the computer but always have challenges relative to the application of ICT in Mathematical concepts and problem-solving" ...FP1, FP4 & FP5: Core Mathematics & ICT teachers.

Moreover, the findings further revealed as follows:

..."In my experience as a teacher, application of ICT tools in teaching and learning mathematics stimulates a collaborative and positive learning attitude among students" ...FP2 & FP3: Core Mathematics & ICT teachers.

In furtherance, data solicited further emerged as follows:

..."Based on my experience in the classroom, I have quite observed that incorporation of ICT in teaching and learning mathematics stimulates positive attitude and interactive learning environment except learners often have difficulties in the application of theoretical knowledge into pragmatic and practical-based learning with the use of ICT equipment" ...FP6: Mathematics teacher.

However, deducing from the perspective of the findings suggest that incorporation of ICT in teaching and learning Mathematics stimulates a positive attitude and perception and interactive learning environment in spite of students difficulties in relation to the application of theoretical knowledge into practical-based learning skills.

- *Reimbursements of Including ICT Equipment in Mathematics Instruction and Learning*

The overarching tenacity of this section of was to discover the benefits of incorporating ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning in the two senior high schools. To achieve this objective, the researcher asked participants to state the benefits of ICT in teaching and learning Mathematics. However, based on data elicited from the survey, the findings turnout as follows:

...*“In my experience as a teacher, the application of ICT in Mathematics instruction offers a plethora of benefits to both learners and instructors including easy accessibility to teaching and learning materials and resources, promotion of positive, interactive and collaborative system of teaching and learning and also promotes practical based learning through the application of theoretical knowledge”...FP2FP5 Core Mathematics & ICT teachers.*

In furtherance, the findings based on data elicited from the survey further revealed as follows:

...*“From my several years’ experience as a teacher, using ICT in teaching and learning Mathematics provide numerous benefits such as mobility and easy access to education through virtualization, enhances students conceptual understanding and cognitive development, it enhance efficient lesson planning and the quality of content delivery”...F1 & F3.*

Moreover, results from the findings further revealed that:

...*“In my experience as a teacher, incorporation of ICT in Mathematics education and learning offer many benefits to both teachers and students. For instance, ICT offer innovation solutions to Mathematical problems such as the use of GeoGebra, it enhances safety, security, flexibility and efficiency in lesson planning and delivery and support multidimensional learning”...FP4 ICT teacher.*

...*“I have more than ten years’ experience in teaching and based on my experience and observation, incorporating ICT in teaching and learning Mathematics offer numerous benefits to all the stakeholders in the educational environment including both students, teachers, examiners and circuit supervisors. For instance, ICT increase access to the internet for information and research, ICT support Mathematics concepts and theories including the constructivists’ theory and also enhances creative and innovative learning through the application of knowledge”...FP6 ICT teacher.*

In general, results from the findings suggest that incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instruction offer numerous benefits major stakeholders in the educational environment including, students, teachers, examiners and supervisors that ultimately enhances efficiency, flexibility and time saving in academic activities.

- *Barriers & Challenges of Incorporating ICT in Teaching & Learning Mathematics*

In this section, the researcher explored the barriers and challenges that strain incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instruction in the two selected senior high schools based on teachers’ perspective. However, based on data elicited from the interview, the following barriers and challenges were explored.

...*“Based on my experience as an ICT teacher, some of the challenges we experience include in adequate infrastructure, lack of professional ICT training for teachers, time and financial constraints relative to cost of accessing internet and resources, professional knowledge and skills gap of teachers”...FP1, FP3 & FP4: ICT & Core Mathematics teachers.*

In addition to the findings, data elicited from the survey emerged further that some of the barriers and constraints were recounted as follows:

...*“The primary challenge we encounter in terms of incorporating ICT in teaching and learning Mathematics are based on deficit curriculum materials. Other include technical related challenges, teachers’ knowledge, attitude and perception in relation to the benefits and challenges associated with the use of ICT tools in teaching and learning activities also affect their commitment and willingness to incorporate ICT or otherwise”...FP2 & FP6. Mathematics & ICT teachers.*

Finally on the barriers and encounters impeding the incorporation of ICT Mathematics education and learning, results from the findings revealed further as follows:

...*“Based on my experience as a teacher, some of the problems I do face in the classroom is centralized on learners’ inability to apply conceptual knowledge or translate theoretical knowledge into practical-based learning through the computer due to poor IT background”...FP5 Core Mathematics teacher.*

However, deducing from the perspective of the findings, there a lot of challenges impeding effective incorporation of ICT to facilitating Mathematics instructions with increasing cause for concern going forward and thus require remedial and countervailing mechanisms to redress the challenges

➤ *Quantitative Data Analysis*

The quantitative analysis of data elicited from the survey are mainly explanatory and statistically descriptive with the application of frequencies, means, median and standard deviations as tools of analysis to present illustration of results from the findings in a summarized format.

➤ *ICT Infrastructure & Its Effect in Teaching & Learning Mathematics*

To achieve the objective on the effect of ICT infrastructure and its effects on Mathematics instructions, the following assertions were made during the inquiry. ICT promotes efficient, interactive and collaborative teaching & learning, ICT promotes pragmatic and practical-based teaching and learning Mathematics. ICT improves mobility & easy access to education through electronic and virtual platforms, ICT helps improve learners’ numeracy, logic & critical skills, ICT promotes positive learners attitude & perception about Mathematics, ICT improves learners’ problem-solving skills & cognitive proficiency, ICT ease my understanding of Mathematics concepts compared to the rote instruction system, ICT makes easy accessibility to Mathematics soft wares for better understanding and with ICT, we can learn Mathematics through visualization of concepts.

Table 4 Responses on the Effects of ICT in Teaching & Learning Mathematics in SHS

Parameter	N	Mean	Median	Std
Strongly Disagree	80	8	6.5	6.67
Disagree	105	10.5	10.5	6.17
Neutral	208	20.8	22	6.79
Agree	340	34	31	15.8
Strongly Agree	1007	100.7	98	15.5

Source: Research Findings, 2023.

As depicted in table3, the researcher sought to ascertain the effect of incorporating ICT Equipment in Mathematics instruction and learning. Data elicited from the survey divulged that participants with (N=80; M=8; Med=6.5& SD=6.67) Strongly Disagree with the assertions made by the researcher, (N=105; M=10.5; Med=10.5 & SD=6.67) Disagree, participants with (N=208; M=20.8; Med=22 & SD=6.79) were neutral or uncertain; (N=340; M=34; Med=31 & SD=15.8) Agree while participants with (N=1007; M=100.7; Med=98 & SD= 15.5) Strongly Agree with the assertions made by the inquirer in the survey. Analysis of data from the findings seeks to interpret that the highest mean score from the survey is M=100.7 with a standard deviation of SD=15.5. This seeks to suggest that majority of students from the survey from whom sample was taken and data solicited strongly agree that incorporation of ICT infrastructure in Mathematics instructions play a profound and inextricable role relative to enhancing leaners conceptual understanding of Mathematics concepts with improved pragmatic and practical based teaching and learning, problem-solving, logic and critical thinking skills with improved accessibility to education through electronic and virtual learning systems.

➤ *Objective 2: The Available ICT Infrastructure Support Effective Teaching and Learning Mathematics based on Teachers Experience.*

The objective was to ascertain whether the available ICT infrastructure in the Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region support effective Mathematics instructions based on teachers experience. To ascertain teachers response in order to accomplish this objective, the following assertions were made during the survey; ICT improves efficient lesson planning & effective content delivery, ICT improves quality of teaching & learning, enables learners carry their education in their pockets, ICT improves innovation & collaborative teaching & learning, ICT enhances the quality, safety, efficiency & flexibility in Mathematics instructions, ICT increases the accessibility of teaching & learning materials through the internet, ICT supports many Mathematics concepts & formulae including 2D&3D charts & GeoGebra, ICT support multidimensional learning & active classroom participation , and ICT enables learners translate theoretical knowledge into practically-based learning skills.

Table 5 Teachers Response on the Effect of ICT in Teaching & Learning Mathematics

Parameter	N	Mean	Median	Std
Strongly Disagree	1	0.11	0	0.33
Disagree	4	0.44	0	0.73
Neutral	17	1.89	1	2.08
Agree	62	6.89	7	3.72
Strongly Agree	240	26.67	27	5.39

Source: Research Findings, 2023.

As depicted in table 4, the researcher sought to ascertain whether the available ICT infrastructure in the Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region support effective teaching and learning Mathematics based on teachers experience. However, data elicited from participants of the survey emerged that participants with (N=1; M=0.11; Med=0 & SD=0.33) Strongly Disagree, participants with (N=4; M=0.44; Med=0 & SD=0.73) Disagree, participants with response frequency, mean,

median and standard deviation (N=17; M=1.89; Med=1 & SD=2.08) were neutral in their responses while participants with response frequency, mean, median and standard deviation (N=62; M=6.89; Med=7 & SD= 3.72) Agree while participants with response frequency, mean, median and standard deviation (N=240; M=26.67; Med=27 & SD=5.39) Strongly Agree to the assertions made by the researcher during the inquiry.

In general, results from the findings is skewed in favor of participants with the highest response frequency of 240 with mean score 26.67 and standard deviation 5.39 who strongly agree with the assertions made during the survey. Deducing from the perspective of the findings seeks to interpret that virtually all teachers confirmed the assertions that the available ICT infrastructure support effective teaching and learning activities.

➤ *Objective 3: Teachers Professional Competence towards Incorporating ICT in Teaching and Learning Mathematics in the Fanteakwa North and South Districts.*

To ascertain this objective, the researcher sought to explore teachers' knowledge and professional competence towards incorporating ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning in Senior High Schools in the Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region based on the perspective and experience of teachers. To achieve this objective, the researcher made the following assertions in the survey. Teacher's ability to integrate ICT tools is determined by their ability to adjust to new innovations, teacher's professional competence play a critical role in promoting quality & consistency of lesson delivery, effective incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instructions is determined by instructors' 'professional awareness and expertise, teachers pedagogical knowledge and skills are the supporting for effective integration of ICT in Mathematics, teachers professional attitude & passion influence their determination to integrate ICT in teaching & learning Mathematics, teachers professional skills in ICT enhances interactive & collaborative learning, teachers professional competence stimulates innovation & creativity of new ideas in using ICT tools and teachers professional skills and competence defines the quality of lesson planning and content delivery. Responses from the survey is presented in table 5 as follows;

Table 6 Responses on Teachers Professional Competence towards Incorporating ICT in Teaching & Learning Mathematics.

Parameter	N	Mean	Median	Std
Strongly Disagree	6	0.75	0	1.16
Disagree	9	1.13	0.5	1.55
Neutral	27	3.38	3	2.62
Agree	50	6.25	6.5	3.10
Strongly Agree	196	24.5	26	5.78

Source: Research Findings, 2023.

In table 5, the researcher explored responses on teachers' professional competence towards assimilating ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning in the Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region. However, data solicited from participants turnout that participants with response rate, mean, median & standard deviation (N=6, M=0.75, Median=0 & SD=1.16) strongly Disagree with the assertions made by the researcher in the survey, while participants with response rate, mean, median and standard deviation (N=9, M=1.13, Median=0.5 & SD=1.55) Disagree, participants with (N=27, M=3.38, Median= 3 & SD= 2.62) were neutral in their response choice while participants with (N=50, M=6.25, Median=6.5 & SD= 3.10) Agree while participants with (N=196, M=24.5, Median=26 & SD= 5.78) strongly agree with the assertions made during the findings.

In general, based on data elicited from the survey, results from the findings are skewed in favor of participants with the highest response rate as well as mean, median and standard deviation including; N=196, Mean=24.5, Median=26 and standard deviation 5.78 who strongly agree with the assertions made by the researcher. The analysis seeks to interpret that virtually all participants from whom data was solicited from the survey confirmed the assertion that teacher's professional knowledge and competence significantly determines teachers' efforts towards incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning.

➤ *Objective 4: Expected Outcome of Assimilating ICT Equipment in Mathematics instruction and learning in Senior High Schools.*

The researcher sought to ascertain the expected outcome of assimilation of ICT tools in Mathematics education and learning in Senior High Schools in the Fanteakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region based on teachers experience. To achieve this objective, the researcher made the following assertions during the inquiry. Using ICT tools improves the health & convenience of Mathematics education and learning, with the aid of ICT, students perform better in Mathematics than the conventional rotary approach, with the aid of ICT, learners can integrate & apply theoretical knowledge into practical-based learning skills, with the application of ICT in Mathematics, it helps improve learners cognitive proficiency and problem-solving skills, ICT improves accessibility of teaching and learning resources & materials and ICT integration of ICT helps improve general academic performance of learners.

Data elicited from the survey is illustrated in table 6 below.

Table 7 Responses on the Expected Outcome of Assimilating ICT t in Teaching & Learning Mathematics in Senior High Schools.

Parameter	N	Mean	Median	Std
Strongly Disagree	7	1.17	1	1.33
Disagree	5	0.83	0.5	1.17
Neutral	20	3.33	3	3.01
Agree	61	10.17	9.5	2.48
Strongly Agree	123	20.5	23	5.96

Source: Research Findings, 2023.

Depicted in table 6 constituted results of data analysis from the findings. The researcher sought to explore the expected outcome of incorporating ICT into Mathematics education and learning. However, based on data solicited and analyzed from the findings, it merged that participants with response frequencies, means, median and standard deviations including; (N=7, M=1.17, Med=1 & SD= 1.33) Strongly Disagree, (N=5, M=0.83, Med=0.5, SD=1.17) Disagree, (N=20, M=3.33, Med=3, & SD= 3.01) were neutral, (N=61, M=10.17, Med=9.5 & SD=2.48) while participants with (N=123, M=20.5, Med=23 & SD=5.96) Strongly Agree with the assertions made during the inquiry. Deducing from the perspective of results from the findings, it seeks to suggest that data obtained and analyzed as well as results from the findings are skewed in favor of participants who strongly agree with the assertions made with highest response rate of N=123 with mean score of 20.5, median 23 and standard deviation 5.95 respectively. The analysis therefore seeks to interpret that incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instructions has advantageous and crucial impact on the outcome of students' academic performance in Mathematics.

➤ Discussion of Key Findings

This section of the study discusses results from key findings in line with relevant scholarly literature relative to the subject matter.

• Participants Sociodemographic Data

Deducing from results from the research findings in relation to participants' gender, results from the findings emerged that both sex constituted partakers of the survey. Which pursues to demonstrate that outcomes from the findings are free from any form of biasness. However, the skewed results in favour of female participants is reflection on the female dominated population structure of the research area which is consistent with the Population and Housing Census description of the Ghana Statistical Service (GSS, 2021). Moreover, on participants' age, 53% constituted the highest participants with age range of 15-20 years. The significance of age as a biological and social construct determines individuals' experience, knowledge and conceptualization of ideas and concepts and the ability to think and make deductions and construction of knowledge based on learners' experience as demonstrated by the post-modernism theory (Kalla, 2006).

• Availability of ICT infrastructure in Teaching and Learning Mathematics

Relative to the availability of ICT infrastructure in support of Mathematical instructions, results from the findings demonstrated the availability ICT tools and infrastructure including Monitor, keyboard, mouse, system units and projectors. However, a cursory look at empirical literature demonstrates that availability as well as the integration and use of ICT tools and infrastructure in Mathematical instructions has a significant and profound effect on learners performance and academic achievement as demonstrated in the case of and Finland and Singapore whose educational systems have been adjudged the best globally due to students' remarkable academic achievement in Science and Mathematics education anchored on technological affordances (Tan, Low, & Hung, 2017). This is also corroborated with the findings of (Das, 2019) where he asserts that availability and integration of ICT tools in Mathematical instructions stimulates innovation in teaching and learning activities and as well promotes efficiency of lesson planning and content delivery, cooperative, collaborative, pragmatic and practical-based learning environment with immediate feedback.

• Determinants of Incorporation & Use of ICT in Mathematical Instruction

Results from the inquiries discoveries grounded on the determinants of incorporation and use of ICT in Mathematical instruction revealed an array of dynamics that impact instructors amalgamation of ICT tools or otherwise in Mathematics instruction and learning some of which included teachers professional knowledge & competence, availability of teaching and learning materials and resources as well as both students and teachers passion, attitude, perception, commitment and willingness to incorporate ICT tools to or otherwise. This result is consistent with the theoretical arguments underpinned by this study including the Technological Acceptance Model and Theory of Planned Behavior embedded on some psychological and social dynamics that influences characters' resolution to adopt and use a new scientific invention comprising perceived risks, ease of use, perceived benefit & usefulness, idiosyncratic and expedition circumstances correspondingly (Arthur, 2020).

- *Incorporating ICT in Mathematics Instruction and its Influence on Learners Attitude & Perception about Mathematics.*

From the perspective of results from the findings suggest that incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning stimulates an affirmative attitude and perception and interactive learning environment in spite of students difficulties in relation to the application of theoretical knowledge into practical-based learning skills. However, the results seeks to suggest that incorporation of and use of ICT tools in Mathematical instruction has a positive influence on learners' attitude and perception. Results from this findings is consistent with (Bam, 2021) relative to the integration of ICT in instructing Mathematics based on the perspective of learners revealed that incorporation of ICT has a affirmative impact learner's attitude, perception and conceptual underrating of mathematics. This is further corroborated by (Annie, 2021) based on participants positive attitude, ICT competence, access to ICT tools, teaching style and confidence level as key predictors of ICT integration in Mathematics instruction. The findings revealed a positive correlation between positive attitude, ICT competence and access to ICT tools in Mathematics instruction and learning in senior high schools.

- *Benefits of Incorporating ICT tools in Mathematics Instruction*

In general, results from the research findings suggest that incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instruction offer numerous benefits to major stakeholders in the educational landscape including, students, teachers, examiners and supervisors that ultimately enhances efficiency, flexibility and time saving in academic activities including facilitation of Mathematical instruction. In line with results from the findings of (Grewal, 2020), the advancement and proliferation of digital technology has numerous benefits including its contribution towards transformation of the global educational system from conventional and mass education system to a revolutionized system with easy access to academic resources through internet access, virtual & online education, information access, sharing and storage of academic materials and ease in communication which ultimately enhances academic activities and consequently improved academic performance of learners. Moreover, this is corroborated by (Joshi, 2017) where is clearly established that integration of ICT tools in education also contributes significantly to transformation of the educational environment from conventional to virtual and mobile learning systems that allow students to carry their education in their pockets with improved learning access and efficiency with improved quality of learning outcomes (Joshi, 2017). Also consistent with (Mukhdoomi, 2020), he asserts that the contemporary digital and virtual society brought about by technological advancement with competing demands for computers, smart phones, iPad, tablets, laptops and other gadgets such as simple four functional calculators, scientific calculators, and algebra systems all constitute innovations that drive easy teaching and learning activities through internet access, ease in communication, online education, easy access to academic materials for research and development, easy sharing and storage of academic files and virtual or e-learning platforms that enable students access their every time and everywhere (Mukhdoomi, 2020).

- *Barriers and Challenges Impeding Incorporation and Use of ICT in Mathematics Instruction.*

Based on results from the outcome of the findings, there are a plethora of challenges impeding effective incorporation of ICT to facilitating Mathematics instructions among which include; lack of adequate infrastructure, lack of professional ICT training for teachers, time and financial constraints relative to cost of accessing internet and resources, professional knowledge and skills gap of teachers, deficit curriculum materials, technical related challenges, teachers' knowledge, perceived benefits and perceived risks in relation to the application of ICT resources to Mathematics instruction and learning and learners inability to apply conceptual knowledge or translate theoretical knowledge into practical-based learning through the computer due to poor IT background. In line with this results, (Arthur, 2020) notes that an array of challenges or barriers that hamper efforts towards incorporating and utilizing technological devices for Mathematics instruction and learning most particularly in third world countries with resource constraints. These include changes in curriculum and policy frameworks by government, inadequate curriculum materials and resources, ICT infrastructure deficit, time and financial constraints in relation to the costs associated with the procurement and adaption of the right and appropriate technological tools and infrastructure. Moreover, it is re-echoed by (Chong, Horani, & Daniel, 2005) that some of the barriers that affect incorporation and usage of ICT resources in Mathematics instruction include; inadequate time to incorporate ICT tools in teaching and learning activities, lack of professional teacher training relative to ICT, lack of professional skills, knowledge and competence in relation to how to assimilate and use ICT resources in teaching and learning Mathematics in the classroom. However, identification of these barriers and challenges stimulates the need for remedial measures and countervailing interventions to ameliorate these challenges with improved performance of learners in Mathematics.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ *Introduction:*

The fifth chapter provides an overview of the investigation's outcomes, a conclusion, and recommendations for further research.

➤ *Summary of Key Findings*

The summary of results from key outcomes are presented in harmony with the exploration goals and queries developed to address the investigation problem on poor academic performance students in Mathematics. However, in line with results from the research findings on the availability of ICT infrastructure and resources in the selected senior high schools revealed the availability but inadequate ICT infrastructure and resources in the selected senior high schools for the survey. Consistent with results from the research findings in line with the second objective relative to the ICT tools that support effective teaching and learning activities, results from the findings revealed the available ICT tools to include desk/table top computers, monitors, system units, mouse, connecting cables and projectors. These were identified as the available ICT tools that support teaching and learning activities in the two senior high schools.

In furtherance, based on results from the research findings consistent with the third objective on teachers professional competence and its effect in incorporating ICT resources in Mathematics instruction and learning revealed that teacher's professional knowledge and competence significantly determines their efforts and commitment towards incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning in Senior High Schools.

Moreover, in line with the fourth objective relative to the outcome of incorporating ICT in Mathematics education and learning revealed that incorporation of ICT in Mathematics education has constructive and substantial impact on the outcome of students' academic performance in Mathematics and as well stimulate positive, interactive, collaborative and multidimensional learning environment. In addition to teachers knowledge and professional competence, other factors were also identified as determinants or dynamics that impact instructors assimilation of ICT tools or otherwise in training and learning Mathematics which included availability of training and learning materials and resources as well as both learners and teachers passion, attitude, commitment and willingness to incorporate ICT tools or otherwise.

Results from the findings further revealed that incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instruction offer numerous benefits major stakeholders in the educational environment including, students, teachers, examiners and supervisors that ultimately enhances efficiency, flexibility and time saving in academic activities.

Finally on the fifth objective with respect to the barriers and encounters distressing the assimilation and usage of ICT in Mathematics education and learning, results obtained from the findings revealed there are a plethora of challenges impeding effective integration of ICT for Mathematics instructions and these included inadequate infrastructure, lack of professional ICT training for teachers, time and financial constraints relative to cost of accessing internet and resources, professional knowledge and skills gap of teachers, deficit curriculum materials. Moreover, other challenges included technical related challenges, teachers' knowledge, attitude and perception in relation to the benefits and challenges associated with the usage of ICT resources in training and learning tasks also affect their commitment and willingness to incorporate ICT or otherwise coupled with inability of students to apply conceptual knowledge or translate theoretical knowledge into practical-based learning through the computer due to poor IT background. This stimulates an urgent need for remedial and countervailing interventions to address the challenges going forward.

➤ *Research Implication*

The integration and application of digital technology infrastructure in the educational curriculum of many developing and resource constrained economies is less explored with literature deficit in the Ghanaian context. However, the outcome of the findings will be more impactful a key repository material to the general public and specifically in academic environment as a source of reference for further studies.

In furtherance, the significance and benefits of integrating and incorporating ICT into the educational curriculum and its upshot on learners' academic attainment are less explored in the Ghanaian educational curriculum. It is therefore anticipated the outcome of the study will provide insight and contribute towards enhancing public knowledge relative to the benefits offered by electronic devices used in communication and information retrieval and the need to leverage the wave and proliferation of the digital revolution.

Moreover, it was also observed that a plethora of factors affect incorporation and usage of ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning in the classroom including lack of adequate curriculum materials. It is however anticipated the outcome of the study will highlight the need for policy recommendations with countervailing mechanisms to address the challenges.

➤ *Conclusion:*

It is imperative to state that both Mathematics and Information and Communication Technology constitute important disciplines of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education that play an inextricable and profound role in stimulating innovation and creativity in a society riddled with numerous challenges in which the educational environment is not exempted. The overarching purpose of this study was to examine the effects of ICT in Mathematics instruction and learning in Senior High Schools with focus on the Fantakwa North and South Districts in the Eastern Region. The study employed both purposive and random sampling techniques and primary data elicited with the aid of structured questionnaire designed based on a five point Likert Scale and semi-structured interview. Data elicited from the field was analyzed with both descriptive and explanatory techniques. Frequencies, means, medians, standard deviations and graphs were employed as tools of analysis with the help of the Excel program and utilizing the results' perspective, suffice to conclude that incorporation of ICT in Mathematics instructions has constructive and substantial impact on the outcome of students' academic performance in Mathematics and as well stimulate positive, interactive, collaborative and multidimensional learning environment despite several barriers and challenges including lack of curriculum materials as well as professional skills and knowledge gaps due to lack of professional training programs. This is therefore closely followed with recommendations to help address the challenges.

➤ *Recommendations:*

The recommendations grounded on the outcome of the verdicts are as follows; government must ensure adequate supply of educational infrastructure and resources including curriculum materials to engender effective teaching and learning activities.

Moreover, there is the need for government provide professional training programs to teachers in order to breach skills and knowledge gaps among teachers. This will ultimately ensure increasing efforts and commitment towards incorporating ICT in Mathematics instructions.

In furtherance, government together with the ministry of education and Ghana Education Service must ensure effective and timely supervision to ensure teachers adequately incorporate ICT teaching and learning activities. In this case, government can award best performing teachers and also penalize non-performing ones. This will ultimately help boost the effectiveness of coaching and learning activities in the educational sector.

More importantly, government must prioritize policies towards leveraging the wave and proliferation of the rising trend of the society with its numerous benefits. This sets the trajectory as part of efforts towards transforming various sector of the economy including the educational sector.

➤ *Recommendations for Future Studies*

Based on results obtained from the current findings, there is the need for future researchers to focus on the bearing of digital technology on learners' academic attainments.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdelrahman, A. &. (2020). Logistics and Supply Chain Management. Jonkoping, Sweden: Jonkoping University.
- [2]. Adatsi, I. P. (2013). A Study of the Relationship Between Student's Biopsychosocial Problems and Academic Performance in Ghana: A Case Study of Senior High Schools in Tema Metropolitan District. Accra: Methodist University.
- [3]. Afum et al. (2020). Green Manufacturing Practices and Sustainable Performance Among Ghanaian Manufacturing SME's: The Explanatory Link of Green Supply Chain Integration. Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal, PP. 1477-7835.
- [4]. Agyei, D. D., & Voogt, J. (2010). ICT use in the Teaching of Mathematics: Implications for Professional Development of pre-service Teachers in Ghana. Springer, PP. 1-17.
- [5]. Akhtar, I. (2016). Research Design. New Delhi: Delhi UBS Publishers.
- [6]. Albadi, A., & David, S. A. (2019). The Impact of Activity Based Learning on Students on Motivation and Academic Achievement: A Study Among 12th Grade Science and Environment Students in Public Schools in Oman. Specialty Journal of Knowledge Management, Vol. 4(4), PP. 44-53.
- [7]. Amponsah-Tawiah, A. (2020). An Investigation into Pupils' Experiences of Solving Non-Routine Mathematics Problems: A Case Study of Ghana International School. Accra: University of Ghana.
- [8]. Andrzej, S. (2012). Logistics and Supply Chain Management. Poland: ResearchGate. net Publications.
- [9]. Arthur, B. A. (2020). Ghana's Road to Cashless Economy: The E-zwich Experience. RISUS-Journal on Innovation and Sustainability, Vol.1(1), PP-52-67.
- [10]. Awuku, F. (2019). Prospects and Challenges of Cashless Economy in Ghana. Accra: University of Ghana.
- [11]. Bam, P. (2021). Integration of ICT in Teaching Mathematics: Students Perspectives. Kirtipur, Kathmandu, Nepal: Tribhuvan University.
- [12]. Berg, J. P. (2012). Highly Competitive Warehouse Management (International Edition ed.). The Netherlands: Management Outlook Publications.
- [13]. Berhane et al. (2020). Effectiveness of Concept Mapping Based Teaching Methods on Grade Eight Students' Conceptual Understanding Photosynthesis. EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education, Vol. 16(12), PP. 1305-8223.
- [14]. Boadu, P. (2014). Embracing Green Supply Chain Practices in the Construction Industry; The Case of Construction Firms in the Kumasi Metropolis and Its Environs. Research Journal of Management, Vol.2(6), PP. 2347-8217.
- [15]. Bohdan, A. (2018). Green and Reverse Logistics as the Tools for Improving Environmental Sustainability. Berlin, Germany: JamK.fi.
- [16]. Charlotte Dannenberg, S. E. (2015). Learning Paths of Teachers, Studying: Intention, Activities and Outcome to Understand Teacher Learning at the Work Place. Netherlands: University of Twente.
- [17]. Cohen et al. (2007). Research Methodology in Education. Madison Avenue, New York USA: Routledge-Taylor and Francis Group.
- [18]. Cohen, L. M. (2007). Research Methods in Education. Madison Avenue New York, USA: Taylor and Francis Group.
- [19]. Das, K. (2019). Role of ICT for Better Mathematics Teaching. International Journal of Education, Vol. 7(4), PP. 19-28.
- [20]. Donaldson, S. E. (2011). Teaching Through Problem Solving: Practices of Four High School Mathematics Teachers. Georgia: University of Georgia.
- [21]. Ebenezer Afum, V. Y.-A.-M. (2020). Green Manufacturing Practices and Sustainable Performance Among Ghanaian Manufacturing SMEs: The Explanatory Link of Green Supply Chain Integration. International Journal of Management of Environmental Quality, PP. 1477-7835.
- [22]. Evans, T. (2013). Assessment of the Determinants of Academic Performance of Basic Schools in Wa West District. Accra: University of Ghana.
- [23]. Galinska, M. B. (2017). Total Logistics Management Concepts and Principles in Manufacturing Enterprises. 17th International Scientific Conference Business Logistics in Modern Management (pp. PP. 93-105). Poland: ResearchGate Publications.
- [24]. Grewal, B. a. (2020). Impact of Mobile Phone Usage on Academic Performance and Behaviour of Medical Students. International Journal of Medical and Dental Sciences, Vol.9(1), PP. 2320-1118.
- [25]. Gulmez, S. T. (2017). Green Logistics for Sustainability. International Journal of Management Economics and Business, Vol.13(3), PP. 603-612.
- [26]. Gummesson, E. (2004). Qualitative Research in Marketing. European Journal of Marketing, Vol.39(3/4), PP. 309-327.
- [27]. Gunjal, P. N. (2015). Green Logistics: Improving the Sustainability of Logistics in Environmental and Organizational Point of View. International Journal of Science, Technology and Management, Vol.4(3), PP. 122-133.
- [28]. Gustafson, H. G. (2014). Green Logistics in South Africa. South Africa: Umea University.
- [29]. Gustafson, H. G. (2014). Green Logistics in South Africa: A Study of the Managerial Perceptions in the Road Transportation Industry in South Africa. South Africa: Umea University.
- [30]. Jermstipparsert, J. S. (2019). Role of Warehouse Attributes in Supply Chain Warehouse Efficiency in Indonesia. International of Innovation, Creativity and Change, Vol. 5(2), PP.786-798.
- [31]. Jharotia, A. K. (2018). Role of Media in Enhancement of Environmental Awareness. Power of the Media: Shaping the Future (pp. PP. 1-12). New Delhi: Research Gate.

- [32]. Joshi, D. R. (2017). Influence of ICT in Mathematics Teaching. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*, Vol. 3(1), PP. 7-10.
- [33]. Karunaratna et al. (2019). A Study of the Implications of Logistics 4.0 in Future Warehousing: A Sri Lankan Perspective. *International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management* (pp. 1024-1034). Sri Lanka: IEOM Society International.
- [34]. Khan et al. (2020). Green Supply Chain Performance and Environmental Sustainability: A Panel Study. *Scientific Journal of Logistics*, PP. 141-159.
- [35]. Khan, S. A. (2019). The Effects of Green Logistics on Economic Growth, Social and Environmental Sustainability: An Empirical Study of Developing Countries in Asia. *Creative Commons*, PP. 1-18.
- [36]. Khan, Y. Z. (2020). Green Supply Chain Performance and Environmental Sustainability. *Scientific Journal of Logistics*, Vol. 16(1), PP. 141-159.
- [37]. Khanzode, S. a. (2017). A Comprehensive Review of Warehouse Operational Issues. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management*, Vol.26(3), PP. 1-27.
- [38]. Kirgegaard, A. (2012). Music and Transcendence: Sufi Popular Performances in East Africa. *The Finish Society for the Study of Religions*, 48(1), PP. 29-48.
- [39]. Korbel, P. (2015). *Students' Experiences of Mathematics and How they Affect Further Engagement with Mathematics*. Adelaide, Australia: University of Adelaide.
- [40]. Kusi-Sarpong et al. (2016). Green Supply Chain Practices and Performance in Ghana's Mining Industry: A Comparative Analysis Based on DEMATEL and AHP. *International Journal of Business Performance and Supply Chain Modelij*, PP.1-25.
- [41]. Kusi-Sarpong, J. S. (2016). Green Supply Chain Practices and Performance in Ghana's Mining Industry: A Comparative Analysis Based on DEMATEL and AHP. *Internal Journal of Business Performance and Supply Chain Modelling*, PP. 1-24.
- [42]. Lourenco, H. R. (2005). *Logistics Management: An Opportunity for Metaheuristics*. Barcelona, Spain.
- [43]. Maganga, J. (2016). *Factors Affecting Students Pformance : A Case Study of Public Secondary Schools in Ilala District Dare-ES-Sallam, Tanzania*. Tanzania: University of Tanzania.
- [44]. Ministry of Education. (2009). *ICT in Education Policy*. Accra: Ministry of Education.
- [45]. Mohamed, A. M. (2020). *The Role of E-Payment Systems on Economic Growth in Nigeria*. Nigeria: Baze University, Abuja.
- [46]. Mphale, L. M., & Mhlauli, M. B. (2014). Investigation on Student Academic Performance for Junior Secondary Secondary Schools in Botswana. *European Journal of Educational Reserach*, Vol. 3(3), PP. 111-127.
- [47]. Mukhdoomi, F. K. (2020). *The Impact of Smart Phone Addiction on Academic Performance of Higher Education*. Karachi, Pakistan: Munich Personal RePEc Archive.
- [48]. Munot, V. B. (2019). *Research Methodology: A Practical and Scientific Approach*. New York, USA: CRC Press-Taylor and Francis Group.
- [49]. Nguyen, M. L. (2017). *The Impact of Employees Motivation on Organizational Effectiveness*. Vaasa, Finland: Vaasan Ammatikorkeakoulu University of Applied Sciences.
- [50]. Oaya et al. (2017). Impact of Recruitment and Selection Strategy on Employees' Performance. *International Journal of Innovation and Economic Development*, Vol. 3, PP. 32-42.
- [51]. Poku, D. A. (2019). *Analysis of Junior High School Students' Attitudes Toward Mathematics and its Effect on the Academic Achievement*. Accra: University of Ghana.
- [52]. Prezly. (2019). The Relationship Between PR and CSR. *PR Academy*, V. 1, pp 1-7.
- [53]. Reeves, H. (2016). Defining Public Relations's Role in Corporate Social Responsibility Programs. *Summer / Fall*, V. 10, pp 1-19.
- [54]. Rijal, P. (2020). *Causes of Low Performance in Mathematics*. Nepal: Tribhuvan University .
- [55]. Ryan, P. J. (2000). The Mystical Theology of Tijani Sufism and its Social Significance in West Africa. *Journal of Religion in Africa*, Vol.30(2), PP. 208-224.
- [56]. Seroka-Stolka, O. (2014). The Development of Green Logistics for Implementation Sustainable Development Strategy in Companies. *Science Direct*. Vol. 151, pp. PP.302-3029. Poland: ELSEVIER.
- [57]. Shodhganga. (2020, June 10th June, 2020). Shodhganga.infibnet. Retrieved from <http://Shodhganga.infibnet.ac.in/bitstream>.
- [58]. Tety, J. L. (2016). *Role of Instructional Materials in Academic Performance in Community Secondary Schools in Rombo District*. Tanzania: University of Tanzania.
- [59]. Westberry, N. C. (2009). *An Activity Theory Analysis of Social Epistemologies Within Tertiary- Level ELearning Environments*. Newzealand : University of Waikato.
- [60]. Woldeamanuel, Y. W., Abate, N. T., & Berhane, D. E. (2020). Effectiveness of Concept Mapping Based Teaching Methods on Grade Eight Studnets' Conceptual Understanding of Photosynthesis. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, Vol. 16(12), PP. 1305-8223.
- [61]. Yong, K. H. (2009). Contribution of Public Relations (PR) to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): A Review on Malaysia Perspective. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, V 2, pp. 45-48.
- [62]. Zarrinkoob, A.-H. (1970). Persian Sufism in Its Historical Perspective. *Iranian Studies*, Vol.3(3/4), PP. 139-220.

APPENDIXES

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

The questionnaire is designed to facilitate collection of data on the effects of incorporating ICT in teaching and learning mathematics in senior high schools: a case study of Fanteakwa north and south districts in the eastern region. The primary purpose of the exercise is to fulfil an academic requirement for the award of Master of Philosophy in Mathematics Education. I wish to assure you that all responses provided to these questions will be strictly treated with utmost confidentiality and used only for the intended purpose.

Thank you for your cooperation and time.

Please tick (✓) one where multiple response choice is provided.

➤ *SECTION A: Demographic Data*

- Gender Male Female
- Age-group 15-20 21-25 26-30 31-35 36-40

Other Specify.....

APPENDIX A: TEACHERS ONLY

- Are there ICT infrastructure or resources available in the Fanteakwa North and South SHS? If yes, then explain if they are adequate to support effective teaching and learning in the classroom.
.....
.....
- Have teachers adequately incorporate ICT in teaching and learning mathematics? If yes, then explain the impact of that on students conceptual understating as opposed to the conventional rote learning strategy
.....
.....
- Explain in your experience if incorporating ICT has any influence on students attitude and perception about mathematics
.....
.....
- In your opinion, explain the benefits of incorporating ICT in teaching & learning mathematics
.....
.....
- In your experience, state the barriers or challenges affecting the use of ICT in teaching & learning mathematics in the classroom
.....
.....
- Based on the challenges identified, propose recommendations to help mitigate such barriers & challenges
.....
.....
.....

APPENDIX B

➤ Available ICT infrastructure that support *Effective Teaching & Learning Mathematics. Students Only:*

7.0 Based on your knowledge and experience, identify the available ICT tools that support effective teaching and learning Mathematics.

.....

ICT Infrastructure & Its Effect on Teaching & Learning Mathematics	1	2	3	4	5
8. ICT promotes efficient, interactive & Collaborative Teaching & Learning mathematics					
9. ICT Promotes pragmatic & Practical-based Teaching & Learning Mathematics					
10. ICT improves mobility & easy access to education through electronic platforms					
11. ICT helps improve my numeracy, logic & critical thinking skills					
12. ICT cleared my perception, improved my attitude & conceptual understanding					
13. ICT improved my mathematical problem-solving skills & cognitive proficiency					
14. ICT ease my understanding of mathematical concepts as compared to the rote system					
15. ICT make easy accessibility to mathematical soft-wares for better understanding					
16. With ICT, we can learn mathematics through visualization of concepts					
17. ICT improves mobility & accessibility of education through virtual & electronic systems					

APPENDIX C➤ *For Teachers Only:*

ICT Infrastructure & Effective Teaching & Learning Mathematics	1	2	3	4	5
18. ICT improves efficient lesson planning & effective content delivery					
19. ICT improves quality of teaching & learning mathematics & problem-solving skills					
20. ICT enable students carry their education in their pockets through virtualization					
21. ICT improves innovation, interactive and collaborative teaching & learning					
22. ICT improves the safety, efficiency, quality and flexibility of teaching & learning					
23. ICT increases the availability of teaching & learning materials through the internet					
24. ICT support many mathematical concepts & formulae including 2d & 3D charts					
25. ICT support multi-dimensional learning & active participation in the class-room					
26. ICT enable students apply theoretical knowledge into practical learning skills					

APPENDIX D➤ *Teachers Professional Competence in Incorporating ICT*

Teachers Professional Competence in incorporating ICT Tools	1	2	3	4	5
Teachers ability to integrate ICT is determined by their ability to adjust to new innovations					
Teachers professional competence play a role in quality & consistency of lesson delivery					
Effective application of ICT in Mathematics is determined by teachers professional knowledge & skills in ICT					
Teachers professional knowledge & skills are the supporting drivers for effective application of ICT in Mathematics					
Teachers professional attitude & passion influence their determination to incorporate ICT in teaching & learning Mathematics					
Teachers professional skills in ICT enhances interactive & collaborative teaching & learning					
Teachers professional competence stimulates creativity of new ideas in using ICT tools					
Teachers professional skills in ICT defines the quality of lesson planning & content delivery					

APPENDIX E➤ *The Outcome of Using ICT in Teaching and Learning Mathematics*

Outcome of Using ICT Tools in Teaching & Learning Mathematics	1	2	3	4	5
Using ICT tools improves the health & convenience of teaching & learning mathematics in the classroom					
With the aid of ICT, students performs better in mathematics than the rote system of teaching					
With the aid of ICT, students can integrate & apply theoretical knowledge into practical based learning skills					
With the application of ICT in mathematics, it helps improve students cognitive proficiency & problem-solving skills					
ICT improve accessibility to learning materials & resources					
ICT improves academic performance of students in mathematics					